

A case study about Assamese media contribution towards inspiring youths for self reliance professionalism

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Abstract

This paper analyzes discursively the Assamese media contribution towards inspiring youths for self reliance professionalism. The country has been progressing towards self- reliance in any walks of life, for some time now. However special ambitious scheme announced by Prime Minister Narandra Modi. A recent reflection is the service during the COVID 19 pandemic period. And at that time, especially assamese media has conducting various awareness programs to make people self-reliant. We know that fourth pillar in democracy in democratic India is media. Therefore, the media is one of the guides to show the people the path of self-reliance. Self reliance in a general sense is what actually promotes productivity and other economic activities which obviously lead to the development of a country. From time immemorial people have always engaged in different activities such as farming, fishing, and hunting, among others, in order to satisfy their basic needs and enhance their social mobility from one class to another. When an adverse situation befalls us, the importance of self-reliance and self-sufficiency becomes even more evident. This applies everywhere, and especially for states like Assam. Currently, the state is also dependent on imports from other parts of the country for basic daily necessities like fish, eggs, onions, pulses etc. Apart from other essential and non-essential commodities like , medicines, clothes, etc.. The state faces various natural disasters like floods almost every year. However, the main duty of the media is to present and inform the people about the programs undertaken by the state, especially its people to become self-reliant in times of crisis or for any other reason.

Keywords: media, inspiring youths, self reliance, pandemic, promotes productivity

Declaration

On behalf of all author, the corresponding author has declared that the paper submitted here was not submitted elsewhere and no conflict interest.

Introduction

The state of Assam is known as the gateway to Northeast India and it has immense significance in terms of Tourism, Agriculture and Industries. It is also a hot bed of political activities. The steady inflow of visitors and tourists throughout the year keep the state busy. Numerous people of diverse culture and community inhabit Assam. All these factors make the state a favourite with the media. The Assam Media with all its forms is working to serve the people with information, education and entertainment. Media plays a vital role today in any conflict situation. It can play constructive as well as destructive role in the way they present conflict situations and images to the audience. Though in India there have been many conflict situations in the past and present, it can be Role of Media in Assam Kisholoy Choudhury & Pranjit Hazarika said that not much of attempt has been made to study the role of the media, though of late there has been a mushrooming of media houses in the country. These educational institutes play a vital role in promoting start-ups and encouraging them to turn visions into reality. Some of them are offering a variety of courses and programmes that equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge to make their ideas into successful businesses. These institutes are offering courses that cover a variety of topics, from business planning to marketing. They also provide networking opportunities, as well as advice on how to succeed in the business world. The call for self-reliance has touched upon every sphere of the state. There has been an increasing effort to create a new Assam, to utilize its resources and be self-reliant. The Assam government is striving to minimize its imports and transform the state into a manufacturing hub. This has produced multiple market opportunities for innovative startups, but accomplishing the task is not so easy and would require a lot more time than one might assume. There is no denying that the electronic sector is one of the fastest-growing in Assam. With a population of over 1.3 billion people, Assam has a lot to offer in terms of potential for growth in this industry. However, some challenges need to be addressed if Assam is to contribute meaningfully to the development of Assam's electronic sector. One such challenge is infrastructure. While there are

several initiatives underway to address this issue, much more needs to be done for Assam to truly become an electronics powerhouse

Objectives

1. To Discuss the role of assamese media in Promoting Self Reliance Stories.
2. To Discuss the People becoming self-reliance through media

What Are the Different Types of Media?

Media is the term we use to refer to different types of media that provide us with important information and knowledge. Media has always been part of our society, even when people used paintings and writings to share information.

As time passed, people came up with different modes to provide news to the public. Based on the type of medium, their role may be different, but they all exist to communicate to the audience and affect their perceptions. Today, we don't have to travel oceans or wait for a pigeon to get the latest news.

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Different Types of Media

The goal of media is to convey an advertising message to the audience through the most appropriate media channel for their product.

In general, you can classify media in three main categories.

Print Media

This type of news media used to be the only way of delivering information to the public. For the generations of the 80s and 90s, print media was the only media of entertain. People relied on newspapers and magazines to learn everything, from recipes and entertainment news to important information about the country or the world. Print media includes:

Newspapers – printed and distributed on a daily or weekly basis. They include news related to sports, politics, technology, science, local news, national news, international news, birth notices, as well as entertainment news related to fashion, celebrities, and movies. Today’s parents grew up with this type of printed media.

Magazines – printed on a weekly, monthly, quarterly, or annual basis. It contains information about finance, food, lifestyle, fashion, sports, etc.

Books – focused on a particular topic or subject, giving the reader a chance to spread their knowledge about their favorite topic.

Banners – used to advertise a company’s services and products, hung on easily-noticed sights to attract people’s attention.

Billboards – huge advertisements created with the help of computers. Their goal is to attract people passing by.

Brochures – a type of booklet that includes everything about one company – its products, services, terms and conditions, contact details, address, etc. They are either distributed with the newspapers or hand over to people. Check this article to learn more on how to ease the brochure design process [here](#)

Flyers – used mostly by small companies due to the low cost of advertising. They contain the basic information about a company, their name, logo, service or product, and contact information, and they are distributed in public areas.

Broadcasting Media

Broadcasting media includes videos, audios, or written content that provides important or entertaining information shared by different methods:

Television – in the past, there were a few channels sharing various types of content, whereas now we have hundreds of TV channels to choose from. Each channel delivers a different type of content, so you have a separate channel for news, drama, movies, sports, animation, nature, travel, politics, cartoon, and religion. It’s the number one broadcasting media due to its reach to the audience.

Radio – uses radio waves to transmit entertaining, informative, and educative content to the public. Due to its high reach to the audience, radio is widely used for advertising products and services. Radio is one of the oldest means of entertainment, and today people often hear it to find out the weather and traffic while commuting.

Movies – film, motion picture, screenplay, moving picture, or movie has world-wide reachability. It's the best type of mass media to promote cultures and spread social awareness. Movies have always played a huge part in the entertainment world.

Internet Media

Nowadays, we are relying on the Internet to get the news a lot more often than traditional news sources. Websites provide information in the form of video, text, and audio. We can even choose the way we want to receive the news. Types of Internet media include:

Social networks or websites – including Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, Tumblr, LinkedIn, Snapchat, Quora, Reddit, Pinterest, etc. They are user-friendly and widely used by people around the world. Although we can find any news here, they may be misleading because of the lack of regulations on the content shared.

Online forums - an online place where we can comment, message, or discuss a particular topic. Forums allow us to share knowledge with other people with the same interest. That's why it's regarded as the best platform to seek support and assistance.

Podcast – a series of audios focused on a particular topic or theme. We can listen to them on a computer or a mobile phone. It's a platform that allows anyone to share their knowledge and communicate with the world. You can browse some podcast hosting sites to see what fits your needs best.

Brief history of Assamese Media

Print media made its foray in Assam way back in January 1846 in Sivasagar town in the eastern part of the state with the newspaper 'Arunodoy Sambadpatra' – a monthly. Since then media in Assam has completed a considerably high legacy of 175 long years with rich contributions in every field of Assamese society. Thereafter, in a matter of a few decades, several newspapers in the Assamese language followed suit and started serving the masses. However, the majority of them were short-lived and published mostly as monthly or some even once or twice in a year. This was an initiative of the American Baptist missionaries who set up a base in Sivasagar in the 1930s. The initiative was driven by two major objectives. First, the spreading of Christianity among the inhabitants of the region which was even distinctly printed in the newspaper. Second, launch a campaign for the re-introduction of Assamese as the

official language of the British Assam again as it was replaced by Bengali in 1836, a decade before Arunoday was started. This was because the Missionaries realized that preaching and spreading of religion would be much more effective only if it was done in the local prominent language. Thus, even though religion was the primary interest of the publishers, it also helped in reviving and re-establishing Assamese as the official language in 1873. In this regard, the contribution of this newspaper and the publishers were considerable. Apart from being the first-ever newspaper of Assam, Arunoday's importance is far more crucial from another aspect. That is, it had formally accepted that the Assamese language was an independent full-fledged one rather than being a corrupted version of Bengali. It also made it their crusade to establish the language properly in its modern form. Earlier, the British administration was convinced that Bengali should be introduced as the 'official language' rather than Assamese which happened in 1836. However, the Baptist Missionaries worked dedicatedly to develop the language for re-introducing it as the official language of the state. Their efforts along with sincere interests of a few statesmen of the period led by Anundoram Borooah finally resulted in Assamese being reinstated as an official language in 1873. Arunoday was followed by a good number of newspapers including monthlies, weeklies, few dailies though many of them could not survive. This was because of many factors, primarily financial issues and also to a large extent repressive policies of the British government of not tolerating dissent. One prominent newspaper 'Asam Bilasini' was published in 1871. This newspaper enjoys the distinction of contributing the most towards the national freedom movement. This was not the case during its first edition, but only during the second edition between 1913-1924 under a different owner-cum-editor and different place of publication – Jorhat (Barua, 1998). Other notable ones include – Asam Mihir, Asam Darpana, Asam Dipak, Assam News, Asam Bandhu, Mou, Jonaki, Bijuli, Times of Assam, Avahan, Ramdhenu, Banhi, Asom Bonti etc. A few of them were in circulation for several decades. Besides, The Assam Tribune (daily from Guwahati) which was launched in 1939 initially as a weekly from Dibrugarh has been published as in the 82 year (2021). Besides, there are at least three newspapers in Assamese which have and completed more than 60 years of continuous publication till date. These include Dainik Asom from The Assam Tribune group, Dainik Janambhumi and Asom Bani. It is important to note that several newspapers and magazines during the pre-independence period in Assam had such widespread influence and impact on

Self Reliance Story covered by Broadcasting Media of Assam

1. VERMICOMPOSTING

Vermicomposting , a simple biotechnological process of composting where certain species of earthworms are used to transform organic waste into a nutrient-rich fertilizer . ASRLM has adopted it as a good practice that can be replicated as a income generation activity of SHGs. ASRLM in association with Krishi Vikash Kendras and MGNREGA is marching ahead together towards capacity building on organic fertilizer and henceforth paving ways of production and usage of Vermicompost .

A presentation has been given at the 2nd Annual Workshop of Best Practices held in New Delhi on 19th -20th Feb 2018

2. Changing life of an SHG member- RUPA GOSWAMI

Background

Rupa Goswami, a member of Manasha SHG, under Karunabari Block of Lakhimpur started a small dairy Unit in her home coming into a ASRLM- SHG fold . Like any other village women Rupa too could not think beyond the four walls of her house until she became a member of Manasha SHG. After entering into SHG fold she received number of training, which made her contribute towards family income. Being a good homemaker she was confident that she too can do something within her household premises along with the day to day household chores. Animal Husbandry was something she opted for as she could perceive that she can do it with ease and interest. She was also confident that this livelihood option should sustain giving her a profitable business Her journey towards Self Reliance The SHG (Manasha SHG) of which she is a member received Revolving Fund (RF), Community Investment Fund (CIF) and Bank Loan. With regular Saving and interleading the SHG members were able to contribute a good amount in the SHG account. Submitting a Micro Credit Plan (MCP), Rupa managed to avail a loan of Rs. 30,000/- from the SHG for purchasing

Cattle (Jersey). This initial loan was her first journey towards economic independence. By selling the milk she was able to repay her loan and also save money for herself. With the profit she was inspired to take a step further in this livelihood venture by availing another loan from her SHG. Presently her loan amounts to Rs. 1,00,000/- At present, she owns 7 dairy cattle (Jersey) from which she is able to produce 40 litres of milk per day. Apart from villagers of her locality as buyers, she also sells Milk and Milk products like curd, paneer to various hotels in the small township of Laluk, Lakhimpur. She sells the fresh milk @ Rs. 50 per litre. She maintains her livestock with utmost care by providing them with good quality feeds, timely Medicines and Vaccinations and maintaining the hygiene quotient of the Cattle and the Shed. After incurring all the expenses related to her 7 cattle, Rupa manages to make an income of Rs. Rs.29,000/- to Rs. 31,000/- per month.

Way forward:

This lady who started with a simple livelihood option which she could do by herself, now can confidently engage casual workers and labourers to look after her cattle. This venture which gradually evolved into a small dairy unit became an inspiration for many like her in her locality. Rupa aspires to increase her production from 40 litres to 150 litres per day because her dairy products has market demand at Laluk.

3. Building Entrepreneurship -SANDHYA BHAKTA

Background

Sandhya Bhakta a member of Abha SHG, under Karunabari Block of Lakhimpur owns a bakery unit making an income of Rs. 32000/- per month. After coming into the SHG fold of ASRLM, Sandhya realized that she has ample scope of giving her family business a growth. She realized that her physical contribution and financial assistance can make her a productive member of her family and thereby she will given a due recognition and status. Her journey towards Self Reliance ABHA SHG of which Sandhya is a member had received Revolving Fund (RF) Community Investment Fund (CIF) and also Bank credit of Rs. 1,50,000/-. The SHG also did savings of more than Rs. 40000/- since their formation in 2012. Sandhya took a Loan of Rs. 60,000/- from the SHG to set up the additional of Bakery Unit . She also invested an amount on the purchase of ingredients. Bakery products made by her already had a huge demand , all she needed was to increase the supply which could only happen if she would invest on her unit, ingredients and engage more people in her small unit. The

loan helped her in this prospect and gradually she was able to move from retail business to capture wholesale market . She has also engaged 4 persons in her bakery unit providing them monthly remuneration of Rs.3000. Thus she became a small entrepreneur in her village inspiring her fellow village women.

4. From dream to Reality - Geeta Kurmi

NAME: GEETA KURMI

DOMICILE: GELEKI

DISTRICT: SIBSAGAR

NAME OF PROJECT IMPLEMENTING A
YUVAJYOTI, DIBRUGRAH

TRADE OF SKILL TRAINING RECEIVE

Relation Management- Domestic
domain’.

EMPLOYER : Hinduja Global Serv

(joined in May 2017)

INITIAL SALARY: Rs. 7200

PRESENT SALARY: Rs.17893 (includin

Gita Kurmi comes from a small village in Geleki, Sivsagar with big dreams of making her own identity. Completed her training from M/S NIIT YuvaJyoti, Dibrugarh centre in ‘Customer Relation Management- Domestic Voice BPO domain’.A DDU-GKY Mobilization Camp came as turning point in her life when she got to know about the Skill Training imparted under DDU-GKY programme which is absolutely free. For a girl with poor economic condition and limited resources training in a PIA inder DDU-GKY not only developed her personality, but at the same time opened doors of career opportunities. After completing Gita Kurmi was offered placement in Hinduja Global Services, Siliguri where she joined in May, 2017 with an initial salary of Rs. 7,200 per month. Now she receives a total salary of Rs. 17,893.

5. RSETI UBI Golaghat:

Mrs. Monimala Bora Mohan is a house wife from Mohmaiki Ahu Gaon, Bokakhat and helping her husband in traditional cultivation. Her husband works in a Tea Garden, hence and has the basic knowledge about plantation and farming. For enhancement of their household income they started a Poultry Farm with 200 chicks

but unfortunately incurred loss because of the lack of knowledge in preventive steps. RSETI Intervention came forward as a turning point in their lives when she joined a training on Poultry Farming in RSETI UBI Golaghat. The Training course included precautions to be taken in every step of Poultry farming, best quality varieties, market potentiality and economy of Poultry farming business which is essential to get success in this business. After completion of the training and a clear idea of the Dos and Don'ts of Poultry Farming Mrs. Monimala Bora Mohan expanded their farm to 1300 chicks in the month of November 2016 targeting to sell in the ensuing Bihu Markets in

January 2017. This time she lost only 80 chicks and remaining 1220 grown up and became a size of 2.8 Kgs each when sold to wholesale and retail market @110/- and Rs 200/- per kilo respectively. Now she is earning an average profit of Rs 20000/- after all expenditure from approx 1200 chicks in each batch. She envisages of expanding her business even more by taking loan from bank and hence thrive for a better way of livelihood through entrepreneurship

6. RSETI SBI Chirang:

Babul Debnath comes from economically poor family Basugaon, Bhutiapara. The poor economic condition did not allow him to pursue formal education beyond Class X and thus closing doors of Job opportunities. The only way he could earn bread for his family was by means of starting up something on his own. Some of his acquaintances informed him about RSETI and suggested him to undertake the Free training under SBI-RSETI, Chirang. He enrolled himself for training in Dairy Farming and underwent a 10 days with full interest and dedication. After receiving the training he applied for loan of Rs.225000/- from AGVB, Basugaon Branch to start a dairy business. He owns Milk Cows (Jersey) and supplies milk to the tea stalls of the area and his neighbors. Initial days included struggle with finances but gradually he overcame all of them through hard work and perseverance. Babul Debnath presently supplies 30 to 40 litres of milk every day in the market earning Rs. 60,000/- to 70,000 every month approximately. With the earnings, he regularly repays his EMIs.

The story of People becoming self-reliance through internet media

1. Assam Times

Assam Times Assam, India

The Assam Times is an online newspaper with an emphasis on Northeast India. This is an online newspaper that concentrates on local news from every nook and corner of the region. We solicit articles, news items and your support to make this a success, to focus the Northeast on the rest of the world and contribute in a small way to make more things happen there.

2. MR IJAJ GUIDE

MR IJAJ GUIDE Assam, India

This blog is providing you with brief information about hair loss with products and hair transplants. Discover new research on hair regrowth & reviews for the best hair growth products and treatments to transform your thinning hair to fuller thicker hair. MR IJAJ GUIDE shares all about hair loss resources, guide, tutorial, research paper, and awareness to avoid hair fall. Visit our blog to learn more and take action right now.

3. Halmari » Green Tea

Halmari » Green Tea Assam, India

Halmari Tea is one of the top-ranking gardens in India with 100 years of legacy, now comes with a large collection of finest teas. Their pursuit of quality along with expertise and experience makes them count steadily among the best tea manufacturers in Assam.

4. The Codezine

The Codezine Guwahati, Assam, India

The Codezine is a free resource built with a vision to help people gather knowledge about coding, programming, gadgets, and provide free resources that will help them to learn more about it. Here you will also get about the latest technology happening around the world.

5. Akash Kalita

Akash Kalita Guwahati, Assam, India

Keep up with articles from Akash Kalita

6. Workday Physique

Workday Physique Assam, India

A weight loss coaching website that answers all questions weight loss-related in-depth. Follow for applied knowledge on sustainable diets and exercise.

7. RumiCooks.com

RumiCooks.com Assam, India

RumiCooks is a food blog based in Assam that covers topics on food and recipes basically on Assamese cuisine, news, interviews, food product reviews and places to eat and travel in Assam.

8. Namhah

Namhah Guwahati, Assam, India

Namhah provides the Best Teas from India. Situated in Guwahati, Assam this team gets the best teas from tea gardens and ships it to tea lovers.

9. New Day Class

New Day Class Bongaigaon, Assam, India

English Grammar Rules, Uses, Examples, Vocabulary, Composition, Spoken English, Paragraphs, Essays, Articles, Letters and Applications and Many More.

10. The Sentinel Assam

The Sentinel Assam Guwahati, Assam, India

Read Latest Breaking News, Live in Assam, Guwahati News. The Sentinel is the largest media group - focused on news publishing and only English daily published simultaneously in all North-east India's states.

11. Morung Express

Morung Express Dimapur, Assam, India

The Morung Express is a people-oriented alternative newspaper based in Nagaland that was conceived from the Naga people's historical realities and is guided by their voices and experiences.

12. The News Mill

The News Mill Guwahati, Assam, India

Covers news and current affairs from across Northeast India and beyond. The News Mill is a Guwahati-based digital media organization.

13. Buoyant Lifestyles

Buoyant Lifestyles Guwahati, Assam, India

Buoyant Lifestyles is a travel, fashion and Lifestyle Blog based in Guwahati, Assam.

14. Dimpu Baruah

Dimpu Baruah is a YouTuber from Assam, India. Baruah is 1 million subscribed individual creator from Northeast India on his YouTube channel Dimpu's Vlogs. His other channel is Dimpu Baruah which is based on practical based education

15. Silent Whispers

Silent Whispers Guwahati, Assam, India

Silent Whispers is a lifestyle blog that devise to knit the best of lifestyle tales right from the closet- raw, rich and exquisite.

16. CATLA Broadband Services Blog

CATLA Broadband Services Blog Guwahati, Assam, India

Keep track of all updates, announcements from CATLA, our plans, promotional activities and lifestyle tips through this blog. CATLA is a Broadband Service that aims to provide High Speed Internet connection (Fiber/Wireless) in and around Guwahati with unlimited download/upload data. We have customizable plans for Business, Home, Government offices, and a variety of purposes.

17. BloggingTop

BloggingTop Assam, India

BloggingTop provides Blogging and SEO Tips to take your blog to the next level. It also recommends the best WordPress Themes, Plugins, and blogging tools.

18. Travel and Treasures

Travel and Treasures Assam, India

Traveling information focussing on various treasured places across the globe. Written by Minkon Roy.

19. Prakritik Mantra

Prakritik Mantra Guwahati, Assam, India

Prakritik Mantra Organic Store offers 100% natural organic products that supports health and True Wellness.

20. On An Expedition

On An Expedition Assam, India

Adventure travel blog featuring bike packing stories, destination information, photography that will help you to explore and experience new place

Conclusion

India ranked 63rd out of 190 countries in the World Bank's 'Ease of Doing Business 2020' survey, indicating a favourable business environment in the country. The recent

government reforms, such as allowing private companies to operate in key industries, introducing agriculture initiatives & labour reforms and enabling commercial coal mining, serve as strong pillars to aid development of India's economy and present huge opportunities for the country to become self-reliant. To attract more Foreign Direct Investment in India, it has launched the auction of 41 coal blocks for commercial mining, which will invite greater foreign investments. It has also increased the FDI limits in various sectors such as insurance, aviation, media, and single-brand retail. These steps have proved to be positive as they are highly capital-intensive sectors.

References

1. Lasswell, H. D. (1948). The structure and function of communication in society. In L. Bryson (ed.), *The communication of ideas*. New York: Harper, pp. 32–51.
2. Lievrouw, L., & Livingstone, S. (eds.) (2002). *Handbook of new media: Social shaping and social consequences*. London: Sage.
3. Manovich, L. (2001). *The language of new media*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
4. Meyrowitz, J. (1994). Medium theory. In D. Crowley & D. Mitchell (eds.), *Communication theory today*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
5. Peters, J. D. (1999). *Speaking into the air: A history of the idea of communication*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
6. Barua, S. K. (1998). Asam bilasini : Historical background and assessment. In C. Saikia (Ed.), *A history of one hundred and fifty years of newspapers and literary magazines of Assam (1846-1996)* (pp. 142–155). Guwahati: Celebration committee of 150 years of newspapers in Assam.
7. Bhattacharjya, G. (1998). Role and problems of newspapers in Assam: Pre and Postindependence era. In C. Saikia (Ed.), *A history of one hundred and fifty years of newspapers and literary magazines of Assam (1846-1996)* (pp. 490–517). Guwahati: PRINT MEDIA COMES TO NORTH EAST INDIA
Print Media Comes to North-East India. *Global Media Journal*, 6(1&2).
9. Saikia, N. (2011). *Background of Modern Assamese literature*. Guwahati: Purbanchal Prakasan.
10. Saikia, D. (2019, September 2). Pioneers of Assam's Print Media. *The Hills Times*